

ANALYSIS OF PROSPECTIVE CLASSROOM TEACHERS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS READING BOOK

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Abstract:

Teachers' attitudes towards reading affect their professional development. Since they will be teachers of the future, they have to show that they are worthy to read and show effective literacy behaviors and become successful teachers. The objective of the research is to determine the prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading book. The research model has been employed as survey which is one of the quantitative research methods. The study group of the research consists of 500 prospective classroom teachers receiving education in eight different cities. In the collection of research data, the Attitude Scale for Reading Book was used. Data were collected in December of the year 2017, and in the months of January, February, March, April and May of 2018. The prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading book were analyzed by gender, the city where lived in and the class level. 249 of the prospective teachers participating in the research are third year undergraduate; 251 of them are final (fourth) year undergraduate; 386 of them are female and 114 of them are male. According to the research results, all of the prospective classroom teachers have a positive attitude towards reading book. The attitudes towards reading book which have been adopted by the prospective classroom teachers still receiving their education as third year and final year undergraduate students are at the same level. By gender variable, the scores for attitudes towards reading book are significantly higher in female prospective teachers than it is for males. Considering the city where they live in, the prospective teachers' reading attitudes show a statistically significant difference: Reading attitudes by the prospective teachers living in Istanbul have been found significantly higher than the reading attitude scores for the ones living in other cities. There may be evidence that prospective teachers have a positive reading attitude, use them effectively, have a good general culture level and provide professional development.

Keywords: reading, attitude, reading attitude, motivation, teacher candidate

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1. Introduction

The changes and advancements emerging in science and technology entail a change both in the society and for individuals. Change, innovation, advancement, adaptation and also the continuity of all these can be enabled through education. There are several qualifications and skills which education enables the one to gain. Social, affective and cognitive skills; management and adaptive skills; initiative, comparison and decision-making, and literacy skills are some of these. Compared to the others, literacy skill is the one which triggers, covers and directs many other skills. Reading, as the principal component of literacy, has a key role which shapes human's intellectual life.

Reading should not be considered as a simple linguistic skill. *"Richness that reading provides redounds on human's world of thought and living. Reading constitutes the basis of knowledge acquisition"* (Ungan, 2008, p.219). As an individualized activity, reading has also a function enabling the ones to manage the social facts and/or events in a more rational manner. Reading takes place among the most important ones of the ways of continuous learning and, therefore, fulfilling the needs evolving in time (Odabaş, Odabaş & Polat, 2008, p.433).

Good reader is the person who exhibits positive attitude towards reading and comprehends what he or she reads (Balıcı, Uyar, Büyükkız, 2012, p.966). Emotional traits, experience, desire and needs also have an effect on the approach to reading; and that attitude towards reading act is positive increases the eagerness to read. The concept outstanding herein is reading attitude. Attitude determines the direction of individual's acting in a definite manner under specific circumstances. This general tendency can be demonstrated in two types of action: Individual says something and does something (Shapiro, 2004, p.9). These actions involve the individual's *"predictions, beliefs (amusing, boring, annoying) related to the object and also perspective on it in social aspect"*. As the three elements influencing the formation of attitude, (1) direct experiences related to the object, (2) beliefs in the object, and (3) social norms related to the object (McKenna, Conradi, Lawrence & Jang, 2012, p.84) can be listed. Beliefs, views, values, habits and characteristics are the concepts that are relevant to the concept of attitude, but not synonymous with it. An attitude is a general trend of assessment for an object; on the other hand, a belief or idea is narrower in scope and generally more cognitive in nature (Oskamp & Schultz, 2005, p.18). A person's attitude which means the pattern of behavior he or she has gained in relation to a matter from past to present is specified by the experiences gained within this period. Therefore, it is quite important that the individual gain positive experiences - attitudes in the process of behavior acquisition (Ürün Karahan, 2017, p.67).

Attitude towards reading is the behavior that the one has maintained towards reading, the affective approach the one shows toward reading, which all influence the properties and quantity of reading directly (Başaran & Ateş, 2009, p.77). As a significant element which holds the probability of affecting independent reading, participation in reading activities, the enjoyment and achievement of reading (Logan & Johnston, 2009, p.199), reading attitude is of the key factors attracting people to or detracting them from

reading. It is expected that individuals who have positive attitudes towards reading, are together with the ones reading a lot or lead their lives in environments where there are many readers around also have a positive reading attitude. In educational environment, additionally, teachers are required to give a wide coverage to the arrangements than can have an effect upon the students' attitudes towards reading in a positive way. The reason for this is that the fact of reading provides a basis for each lesson. One of the most fundamental stages of learning process is reading (Kanmaz, 2012, p.62). School and classroom environment support children's performing reading acts, loving to read, tending to read, participating in reading activities and reading attitudes. Classroom teachers, within the process starting from teaching how to read and write, have crucial responsibilities until each student gains independent literacy skill. In fact, in-class activities, educational approaches adopted, and in addition to the educational tools and materials, the teacher's behavior, attitude and manners, language use and communication skills play an active and/or effective role in his or her students' emotional and mental development. *"Attitudes cannot be observed and learnt directly. Teachers must arrange the conditions that are appropriate for mental and motor skills and cognitive strategies to be learnt"* (Schunk, 2000, p.404).

"As reading requires a conscious action in order to initiate and maintain the reader's efforts for comprehension, it can be stated that cognitive capacity only does not ensure reading achievement. Having seen this case leads the researchers to investigate the effect of students' emotive achievements on reading achievement. That the influence of students' affective traits has been gradually increasing makes prompting the development and role of emotional factors involved in the process of reading (including reading attitudes) important." (Buxton, 2017, p. 88).

Designing a rich literacy atmosphere both in and out of the school, and also the classroom teacher's being a role model to his/her students by exhibiting a positive attitude towards reading in addition to the relevant reading activities contribute to his/her students' developing a positive reading attitude, as well. From this viewpoint, teachers' reading attitudes have a more important position in terms of professional development and influence. The literacy behaviors and manners they have exhibited within the process experienced for becoming a teacher, in consequence of "being the teachers of the future", make prospective teachers' reading attitudes highly important. Prospective teachers' showing a positive attitude towards reading and exhibiting influential literacy behaviors are considered substantial in respect to their being successful teachers. In the research, prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading book have been analyzed by the variables of gender, class level, university and the city where they live in. Within the scope of the research, questions to which an answer has been sought are in the following:

1. At which level are the prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading book?

2. Do the prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading book differ according to gender, class level and the city where they live in?

2. Methodology of Research

In the research, as aimed to reveal an existing state, screening model was used. The attitude towards reading book, which is the focus of the research, was tried to be described. The reading attitudes of the research group consisting of prospective classroom teachers were analyzed in its usual circumstances, in a broad perspective and without having any effect.

2.1. Population and Sample

The study group of the research consists of prospective classroom teachers who continue their education in eight different cities of Turkey in the academic year 2018-2017. 249 of the prospective classroom teachers are third year undergraduate and 251 of them are fourth year undergraduate students. 386 of these prospective teachers are female (77, 2%) and 114 of these are male (22,8%). Other demographic features relevant to the prospective classroom teachers were presented in tables. In Table 1, the distribution of the participant prospective teachers by the cities where they receive education / live in was shown.

Table 1: The Distribution of the Cities where the Prospective Teachers Live in

The City where the University to which Prospective Teachers Have Enrolled in is Located	n	%
Kastamonu	81	16,2
Aksaray	75	15,0
Trabzon	88	17,6
Kırıkkale	68	13,6
İstanbul	50	10,0
Uşak	56	11,2
Zonguldak	57	11,4
Ankara	25	5,0
Total	500	

When Table 1 is analyzed, the distribution of the cities where the prospective teachers participating in the research receive their education is seen in this way: The 16% of them receives education in Kastamonu, 15% of them in Aksaray, 18% of them in Trabzon, 14% of them in Kırıkkale, 10% of them in Istanbul, 11% of them in Uşak, 11% of them in Zonguldak, and 5% of them in Ankara. These cities are also remarkable in terms of indicating the geography where the research was realized.

In Table 2, information related to the ages of prospective teachers is presented.

Table 2: The Distribution of the Ages of Prospective Teachers

Age of Prospective Teacher	n	%
19 years old	1	,2
20 years old	49	9,8
21 years old	168	33,6
22 years old	154	30,8
23 years old	92	18,4
24 years old	25	5,0
25 years old	11	2,2
Total	500	

The 10% of 500 students participating in the research is at the age of 20; 34% of them is at the age of 21; 31% of them at the age of 22; 18% of them at the age of 23; 5% of them at the age of 24 and 2% of them at the age of 25. Only one of the prospective teachers is 19 years old.

2.2. Data Collection Tool

In the assessment of attitudes, the values obtained from the responses given to the attitude statements which are presented to individuals (Erkuş, 2003, p.157). Attitude scales can vary. The essential principle is that a clear structure of which everyone reading the content and items at scale can make the same sense out has been designed. In this research, in order to collect the data, "Attitude Scale for Reading Book" developed by Doğan and Çermik (2016) was employed. In the scale, sentences expressing the reading attitude are involved. Studies relevant to the validity and reliability of Attitude Scale for Reading Book were carried out with the participation of 1228 prospective teachers. In order that the psychometric properties of the scale could be determined, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and with the purpose of providing a stronger evidence for the validity of the structure, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to the data were applied. The lowest score that can be received from the scale having been arranged in five-point Likert-type [Totally Agree-5; Agree-4; Partially Agree-3; Agree a bit-2; Disagree-1] and consisting of 36 items is 36 and the highest score is 180. Through the results of reliability analysis carried out in the process of scale development, internal consistency coefficient of the scale was calculated as .88. The scale has a structure of 4 factors: (1) Love to Read Book (2) Benefits of Reading Book (3) Reluctance to and Stress about Reading Book (4) Challenges and Obstacles in Reading Book. One of the items at data collection tool is presented below in terms of setting an example:

**Reading is one of the things I enjoy at most.*

"Attitude Scale towards Reading Book" was decided to be used, with the thought that it could serve the purpose of this research. The scale was used as data collection tool in the research process after a prior consent was received via written communication from the scholars who had developed the scale.

2.3. Data Collection Process

Data of the research were collected within a 6-month time period in total, as in December of the year 2017 and in the months of January, February, March, April and May of 2018. In data collection process, considering that the participants were in different cities, transportation, time and other material factors, different researchers were asked for support. With one researcher from each city which the data were collected from was communicated in written and orally, and those researchers lent assistance voluntarily in the process of applying the scale.

2.4. Analyzing of Data

Data obtained in the research were computerized and analyzed by statistical package. In the evaluation of findings, significance level was accepted as 0,05. In the analysis of differences among groups, Mann Whitney U and Kruskal Wallis H tests were used.

3. Results and Discussion

The attitudes towards reading adopted by the prospective classroom teachers who participated in the research were analyzed as based on the variables of class level, gender and the city where they lived in. Findings attained were classified and compared, and presented in tables.

3.1. Analysis of the Prospective Classroom Teachers' Attitudes towards Reading Book

Ranked form of the findings obtained from the analyses which were carried out in order that prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading book could be determined are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for the Scores of Attitude Scale for Reading Book

Group	Statistics
Mean	144,610
Standard Deviation	24,375
The lowest score	36,00
The highest score	180,00

As specified in Table 3, mean value of the scores which prospective classroom teachers participating in the research obtained from the attitude scale for reading book is 144,610. This score is above the mean and signifies that the prospective teachers have a positive attitude towards reading book. The standard deviation for the scores is 24,375.

Table 4: Findings Related to the Sub-dimensions of Attitude Scale for Reading Book

Sub-Dimensions	N	Mean Value of Score	Standard Deviation
Love to Read Book	500	3,5413	,86235
Benefits of Reading Book	500	4,3190	,85048
Reluctance to and Stress about Reading Book	500	1,5871	,71942
Challenges and Obstacles in Reading Book	500	2,0129	,90262

According to Table 4, the scores that the prospective classroom teachers obtained from the sub-dimensions of the scale are at the level of "Agree" in the sub-dimension of "love to read book"; "Totally Agree" in the sub-dimension of "benefits of reading book"; "Disagree" in the sub-dimension of "reluctance to and stress about reading book" and "Agree a bit" in the sub-dimension of "challenges and obstacles in reading book". These findings point out that the prospective teachers love reading book and find it beneficial; and moreover, they do not regard reading book as an obstacle for themselves.

3.2. Analysis of Prospective Classroom Teachers' Attitudes towards Reading Book by Class Level

The prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading book were compared according to the class levels and relevant results were presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Analysis of Prospective Classroom Teachers' Attitudes towards Reading Book by Class Level

	Group	N	Mean Rank	Rank Sum	U	p
Class Level	Third Year	249	242,56	60398,00	29273,000	,221
	Fourth Year	251	258,37	64852,00		
	Total		500			

When the results of Mann Whitney U Test in Table 5 were examined, it was seen that the scores for the classroom teaching students' attitudes towards reading book did not show a statistically significant difference according to which class level they were at ($p > 0,05$). The scores for the third and fourth year undergraduate students' attitudes towards reading book show similarity.

3.3. Analysis of Prospective Classroom Teachers' Attitudes towards Reading Book by Gender

The prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading book were compared according to gender variable and relevant findings were presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Mann Whitney U Results of the Scores for Attitude Scale for Reading Book According to Gender

	Group	N	Mean Rank	Rank Sum	U	p
Gender	Female	386	270,12	104265,00	14430,000	,000
	Male	114	184,08	20985,00		
	Total	500				

When the results of Mann Whitney U Test in Table 6 are examined, it is understood that the scores for female classroom teaching students' attitudes towards reading book (median=153,00) differ from the scores for male ones' (median=136) as statistically significant ($U = 14430,000$; $p < 0,05$). In other words, females' reading attitude scores are significantly higher than males' reading attitude scores.

3.4. Analysis of Prospective Classroom Teachers' Attitudes towards Reading Book by the City Where They Live in

The participant prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading book were analyzed by the city where the faculty at which they receive education is in and where they live in; attained findings were shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Kruskal Wallis Results of the Scores for Attitude Scale for Reading Book According to the City Where They Live in

The City Where the Prospective Teacher Live in	Group	N	Mean Rank	sd	Chi-square	p
	Kastamonu	81	240,52			
	Aksaray	75	274,33			
	Uşak	56	231,95			
	Trabzon	88	257,63			
	İstanbul	50	308,09	7	18,295	,011
	Kırıkkale	68	221,76			
	Zonguldak	57	214,66			
	Ankara	25	272,56			
	Total	500				

As based on the Kruskal Wallis results given in Table 7, the scores for students' attitudes towards reading book show a statistically significant difference according to the city where they live in ($\chi^2(7)=18,295$, $p<0,05$). In terms of the attitude towards reading, according to the nonparametric post hoc tests, the differences among the scores of the students living in Zonguldak-Aksaray, Zonguldak-Istanbul, Kırıkkale-Aksaray, Kırıkkale-Istanbul, Uşak-Istanbul and Kastamonu-Istanbul are statistically significant ($p<0,05$). Attitude scores for reading of the students who live in Istanbul (mean rank: 308,09) are significantly higher than the scores for reading attitude obtained by the ones in Zonguldak (mean rank: 214,66), Kırıkkale (mean rank: 221,76), Uşak (mean rank: 231,95) and Kastamonu (mean rank: 240,52). The attitude scores for reading obtained by the students who live in Aksaray (mean rank: 274,33) are significantly more than the attitude scores for reading of the students who live in Kırıkkale (mean rank: 221,76) and in Zonguldak (mean rank: 214, 66).

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In this research within the scope of which the attitudes towards reading adopted by the prospective classroom teachers continuing their education as third and fourth year undergraduate students and also receiving their education in different cities are dealt, totally 500 prospective classroom teachers have participated. It has been determined that the prospective classroom teachers have a positive attitude towards reading book. When analyzed in terms of its sub-dimensions related to reading book, it is seen that the highest mean value is for the sub-dimension "benefits of reading book". The results of other researches carried out on this subject have also been reviewed. In the research which Arı and Demir (2013) performed in Çanakale with the participation of 278

prospective classroom teachers, the participant prospective teachers' reading attitudes were found high. The results of both researches are consistent.

The prospective classroom teachers' reading attitudes towards reading book have been analyzed by the class level (third and fourth year). When the findings are assessed, the scores for attitudes towards reading book of the prospective classroom teachers continuing their education as third and fourth year undergraduate students show similarity. Additionally, in the research, the reading attitude scores of prospective classroom teachers have also been analyzed by gender variable. It has been concluded that females' attitudes towards reading book are significantly higher than the male prospective teachers' attitudes, when compared. It has also been realized that this conclusion shows similarity with the results of other researches. In the research which Şenyiğit (2016) carried out in Izmir, it has been detected that the prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading habit are positive; by gender variable, females' reading attitudes are higher than they are for the males. Also, in the research carried out by Arı and Demir (2013), the prospective teachers' reading attitudes revealed out a statistically significant difference according to gender variable. Within the scope of research realized by Dedeoğlu and Ulusoy (2013) in Ankara with 372 prospective classroom teachers receiving education in two different universities, it was determined that the scores for female's reading attitudes were higher than the scores for male's reading attitudes. According to the research by Aslantürk and Saracaloğlu (2010) which investigated the prospective classroom teachers' interest in reading, females' interest is greater than males' interest in reading. In another research, it has been found that the two third of the university students do not read enough, and female students' interest in reading are higher as compared to the males (Saracaloğlu, Yenice & Karasakaloğlu, 2009, p.199). In the research which Arslan, Çelik and Çelik (2009) performed with the prospective physical education and sports teachers, females' attitudes towards reading book have been found more positive according to male prospective teachers' attitudes. As a result of the research by Odabaş, Odabaş and Polat (2008) which was performed with the participation of university students, it was observed that females spent much more time in reading activity, compared to males. Moreover, in the research which Yalınkılıç (2007) carried out with the prospective Turkish-language teachers, female students have a more positive attitude in terms of loving to read book. As a result of the research in which 350 prospective teachers in Elazığ participated, females love reading books more than males do; reading habit and willingness to reading book are more in female students. Although both male and female prospective teachers agree on the necessity of reading book, it has been concluded that the influence and benefits of reading book are more adopted by female students (Gömlüksiz, 2004, p.1). When the results of these researches listed successively and realized in different cities with different study groups are examined, it reveals the fact that females' reading attitudes are higher as compared to males, among the prospective teachers. The shared results of the researches within the scope of which the development of reading skill and affective features for reading were investigated have been in the way that females are more willing to read and also more successful at reading as compared to males. The reason

for this difference arising as relevant to gender variable in the researches is an issue to be considered. Sociological, psychological and individual factors of this result can be discussed, as well. Females' positive approaches to reading in particular can be dealt with the long-term, interdisciplinary research approaches. The geography where individuals lead their lives in, manners of their upbringing, the characteristics of the family, emotive / affective factors, educational level and literacy competencies can affect the approaches and/or attitudes towards reading in a positive or negative way. The reasons and results of this should be analyzed in new researches carried out with the participation of only females and only males.

Another one of the results attained in this research is that the scores for prospective classroom teachers' attitudes towards reading show a statistically significant difference by the city where they live in (i.e., the city where the university at which they receive education is located in). The attitudes towards reading adopted by the prospective teachers living in Istanbul are more positive and higher than the reading attitudes by the prospective teachers who live in Zonguldak, Kırıkkale, Uşak and Kastamonu. The scores for the attitudes towards reading maintained by the students living in Aksaray are significantly more than the reading attitude scores for the students who live in Kırıkkale and Zonguldak. However, in the research by Arı and Demir (2013), the prospective primary education teachers' attitudes towards reading book do not demonstrate a significant difference by the variable of settlement. An investigation on the reasons of this difference can be made, as well. For instance, the cultural facilities of the city where participants live in, prospective teachers' financial means, the conditions for accessing the library and books, education and training specifications at the faculty where they study and also prospective teachers' scholastic aptitude, academic self-efficacy and expectations can have an effect upon these prospective teachers' attitudes towards reading. In order to understand the reasons better, new researches within the scope of which different research methods are employed collectively can be executed throughout the country, at the national level, and with a broad participation. In the same time, by designing different methods of research, it can be analyzed what any other sort of competency and traits are associated with the university students' attitudes towards reading.

Why is the reading attitude so important? Reading attitude is an important sign indicating the one's will to read. Performing a reading act voluntarily and willfully, spending more time to read enable the one who reads a book to be a good reader and also enhances his / her academic achievement. *"It is understood that students appreciate reading since it contributes to school success and personal development and also pleases, in the research by which high school students' reading attitudes have been analyzed. The fact that students who perform a reading act reluctantly underachieve"* (Mitchell & Ley, 1996) has been determined.

Parents, older sisters and brothers, and teachers serve as a model and guide in respect of reading book. Mothers-fathers' and teachers' interest in books and reading have an

influence on the child's reading attitude. It is quite important for these figures to be aware of their responsibilities, to set a good and a positive example (Arıcı, 2009, p.56).

Prospective teachers' having a positive reading attitude can be an evidence in terms of their using the language effectively, having a good level of world knowledge and ensuring their professional development. The literacy competencies and positive attitudes towards the act of reading demonstrated by the classroom teachers, who have an effective role in the development of literacy skills of their students, especially in the elementary school period, will be able to influence the students directly. It is believed that the classroom teachers who are good readers themselves and will be able to serve as a "good model" to their students for reading every time will definitely guide their students' reading life positively, as well.

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